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Abstract. Idioms are considered the main tools in the English language. There are also alternative versions of some idioms with Uzbek expressions. This article analyzes the similarities and differences of phraseological units in English and Uzbek. In addition, figurative expressions in both languages are studied comparatively from semantic, stylistic, and cultural points of view. In addition, the connection of idioms with the culture, values, and national thinking of the people is highlighted. Some idioms in English are shown with corresponding variants in Uzbek based on examples, and the problems in the translation process are fully analyzed.

Key words: Ideology, phraseological units, figurative meaning, stable combinations, linguistic analysis, national-cultural features, semantic compatibility, translation problems.

INTRODUCTION

Language is an important means of reflecting spiritual wealth, worldview and thinking for a nation. One of the aspects that clearly shows the uniqueness of each language is the expressions and idioms in it. Idioms are fixed combinations, the meaning of which does not directly correspond to the grammatical form, used in a figurative sense. They introduce imagery, emotionality, and a national spirit into the speech. Language is an important means of reflecting the spiritual wealth, worldview, and way of thinking of a nation. The uniqueness of each language is especially evident in its expressions and idioms. Idioms are stable combinations used in a figurative sense, the meaning of which does not arise directly from the lexical meaning of the words contained in them. They give the speech imagery, emotionality, and sometimes ironic, and sometimes positive meaning. Despite the fact that English and Uzbek belong to different language families, both languages have idioms, which reflect the history, customs, and cultural values of the people. Moreover, along with various similarities in their grammatical and historical formation, scope of application, and ways of expressing meaning, there are also significant differences.

For example:

- Piece of cake - xamirdan qil sug'urgandek
- Kill two birds with one stone - bir o'q bilan ikki quyovni urmoq

- Under the weather - sillasi qurimoq.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The field of phraseology in linguistics is considered the main branch dealing with the study of ideoms in English and Uzbek. Theoretically, fixed combinations are analyzed in accordance with the classification developed by the Russian linguist Viktor Vinogradov. He divided phraseological units into groups according to their semantic integrity and structural strength, and scientifically substantiated the role of ideoms in the language system.

Another important work on the analysis of idioms in the English language was started by A. V. Kunin, who comprehensively analyzed the structural-semantic features of English phraseology. Also, dictionaries of idioms created by Jennifer Seidl and W. McMordie are an important source in the study of stable compounds in the English language. In this process, along with the origin of ideoms, the scope of their application and methodological features are also widely covered. Regarding Uzbek linguistics, a number of scholars have written and analyzed works devoted to the issues of phraseology. For example, one of the famous scientists in linguistics, Shavkat Rakhmatullayev, developed the theoretical foundations of Uzbek phraseology and analyzed the semantic and grammatical aspects of phraseological units. In addition, the meaning and features of the use of idioms are explained in the explanatory and phraseological dictionaries of the Uzbek language.

In recent years, comparative linguistics has become one of the fields that places more emphasis on the comparative study of ideoms in English and Uzbek. Through research, semantic compatibility, cultural and historical features, and problems in the translation process are mainly analyzed. This process is considered one of the main factors for a deeper understanding of the similarities and differences between the two languages and the development of effective translation strategies.

METHODOLOGY

In this process, the methodology of comparative-linguistic analysis of idioms in English and Uzbek was used. The theoretical basis of the research consists of scientific views on the field of phraseology. In particular, research on the classification and semantic features of idioms used in English linguistics (for example, the works of Jennifer Seidl and W. McMordie), as well as the theory of stable units in Russian linguistics (Viktor Vinogradov) and scientific views in the field of phraseology in Uzbek linguistics (Shavkat Rakhmatullayev's research) play an important role as methodological sources. In particular, expressions in the Uzbek language were compared with their alternative versions in the English language, that is, ideoms, and it was found that some ideoms do not correspond to the meaning of expressions in the

Uzbek language, and some fully correspond. Moreover, since the method of semantic analysis is also considered one of the main factors in this area, the figurative meaning, level of imagery, and national-cultural components of idioms were studied using this method. In addition, the use of idioms in the speech process was analyzed on the basis of examples through contextual analysis. And also, a group of students and students were brought into speech and tested.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the above general information, methods, and styles, it can be said that, first of all, the ideoms of both languages are a source reflecting the national history, culture, and way of life of the people. If ideoms in the English language more closely reflect the development of Western culture, maritime industry, trade, and industry, then ideoms in the Uzbek language are closely related to agriculture, animal husbandry, family relations, and traditional values. For example, the idiom "Kill two birds with one stone," which exists in the English language, fully corresponds in meaning to the Uzbek phrase "Bir o'q bilan ikki qo'yonni urmoq." That is, grammatical formation and imagery are different, but the meaning is the same. For example, the idiom "When pigs fly" in the English language is expressed in the Uzbek language by the phrase "Tuya dumi yerga tekkanda." Here, despite the fact that the means of depiction are different, the content is not realized. At the same time, the features of some ideoms are completely national, and direct translation is impossible. In such cases, it has been determined that the method of contextual or explanatory translation is appropriate. At the same time, ideoms are one of the most complex, stable and reflecting national culture sections of language. Through a comparative study of ideoms in English and Uzbek, it is possible to contribute to the formation of not only linguistic, but also intercultural communication. Also, in this process, direct (literal) translation of ideoms often leads to the reflection of incorrect meaning. Therefore, when translating ideoms, it is important to find an alternative and take into account cultural traditions.

CONCLUSION

Idioms are considered an important phraseological layer of both languages and are inextricably linked with nationality, historical development, and cultural values and traditions. Also, if we summarize by analyzing the above sections, most of the idioms in English and Uzbek are fully or partially consistent in meaning, and moreover, although some idioms differ in terms of imagery, the unity of meaning is preserved. Therefore, it is necessary to use alternative or explanatory translation methods. In general, ideoms in English and Uzbek languages are studied comparatively through the fields of phraseology, translation studies, and intercultural communication, and this situation will serve as the main source for further research.

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